

Carboxylic Derivatives of Bis(1,3-Cyclo-octadienyl) Molybdenum Oxy-dichloride and Bis(1,3-Cyclo-octadienyl) Tungsten Oxy-dichloride

K. M. SHARMA*, K. K. MUNJAL and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 9 March 1979, accepted 11 August 1979

Reactions of dicyclo-octadienyl molybdenum(VI) oxy-dichloride (C_8H_{11})₂ MoOCl₂ (A) and dicyclo-octadienyl tungsten(VI) oxy-dichloride (C_8H_{11})₂ WOCl₂ (B) with mono-, and dicarboxylic acids have been studied and the corresponding carboxylate derivatives of (A) and (B) have been isolated. In these compounds the chlorine atoms of (A) and (B) are replaced by carboxylate groups. IR Spectra and some other physical characteristics of the compounds are reported.

THE ability of cyclo-octadiene to form complexes with halides of group VIII metals has been studied by Chatt and his co-workers (1, 2). So far reported complexes of cyclo-octadiene are mainly addition complexes. In a recent communication we have reported (3) novel cyclo-octadienyl compounds of molybdenum and tungsten, (C_8H_{11})₂ MoOCl₂ (A) and (C_8H_{11})₂ WOCl₂ (B). In these compounds cyclo-octadiene is present as cyclo-octadienyl anion. The present communication deals with the reactions of (A) and (B) with mono- and di-carboxylic acids.

Experimental

Molybdenum oxy-tetrachloride was obtained from Climax Molybdenum Company, U.S.A. 1, 3-cyclo-octadiene was obtained from Koch Light Laboratories, U. K. Tungsten oxy-tetrachloride was prepared by refluxing the oxide of the metal, WO₃, with thionyl chloride. The resultant product after drying under reduced pressure (1-2 mm) and sublimation, yielded tungsten oxy-tetrachloride, WOCl₄, as scarlet needles. Benzene, dried with and distilled over sodium, was further purified by azeotropic distillation with ethyl alcohol. Liquid carboxylic acids were distilled while solid carboxylic acids were recrystallised before use. Dicyclo-octadienyl molybdenum oxy-dichloride (C_8H_{11})₂ MoOCl₂ (B) were prepared by the method reported by us (3). Infrared spectra (in potassium bromide) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 137, Spectrophotometer. Details of the spectra of some representative compounds are given in Table 1. Special precautions were taken to exclude moisture during the preparation of the compounds.

Preparation of Dicyclo-octadienyl Diacetato Molybdenum Oxide :

To 1.25 g (3.15 m moles) of dicyclo-octadienyl molybdenum oxy-dichloride taken in a 250 ml round

TABLE—1

Infrared Spectra (cm⁻¹) of some representative carboxylic derivatives of dicyclo-octadienyl molybdenum oxy-dichloride and dicyclo-octadienyl tungsten oxydichloride in potassium bromide.

(C_8H_{11}) ₂ MoO(OH, COO) ₂	750m, 755w, 900m, 980s, 1315m, 1605m, 1715w, 1780w, 300m, 3005w.
(C_8H_{11}) ₂ MoO(O ₂ CC ₂ H ₅) ₂	755m, 760w, 905m, 975s, 1310m, 1350m, 1410m, 1610m, 1715m, 1750w, 3000s, 3010w.
(C_8H_{11}) ₂ WO(O ₂ CC ₂ H ₅) ₂	750m, 755w, 900m, 982s, 1315m, 1352m, 1415m, 1610m, 1710m, 1750w, 3000s, 3005m.
(C_8H_{11}) ₂ WO(O ₂ CC ₂ H ₅) ₂	755m, 760w, 910m, 980s, 1310s, 1600m, 1690s, 1692w, 180w, 3000s, 3010w.

S=strong intensity, M=medium intensity, W=weak intensity.

bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube, were added 100 ml of the solvent (dry benzene) and 0.38 g (6.33 m moles) of freshly distilled acetic acid. Hydrogen chloride gas did not evolve soon after the addition of acetic acid to dicyclo-octadienyl molybdenum oxy-dichloride taken in dry benzene. The contents were then refluxed at 80°. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas started after about 5. minutes of the refluxing and the refluxing was continued till the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased (50 h). The contents were cooled to room temperature and the blackish blue solution obtained was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure (10-15 mm). The blackish blue product so obtained was repeatedly washed with dry benzene and upon subsequent drying under reduced pressure (1-2 mm) gave a black crystalline compound (87% yield) the analysis of which corresponded with the formula (C_8H_{11})₂ MoO(CH₃-COO)₂ (Found : C, 54.36; H, 6.15; Mo, 21.42

* Present address : Cement Research Institute of India, M-10 South Extension II, New Delhi, India.

TABLE 2—DETAILS OF THE PREPARATION, PROPERTIES AND ANALYSIS OF CARBOXYLATES OF $(C_8H_{11})_2MoOCl_2$

Compound	$(C_8H_{11})_2MoOCl_2$ taken (m moles)	Corresponding carboxylic acid added (m moles)	Reaction time (h)	Colour	Yield (%)	Analytical data (%)		Found. (Calcd) H
						Mo	C	
$(C_8H_{11})_2MoO(O_2CH)_2$	4.50	Formic 9.17	50	Black	90	23.27 (23.07)	51.85 (51.95)	5.70 (5.77)
$(C_8H_{11})_2MoO(O_2CC_2H_5)_2$	4.12	Propionic 8.36	52	Black	86	20.50 (20.51)	56.31 (56.42)	5.90 (5.98)
$(C_8H_{11})_2MoO(O_2CC_2H_7)_2$	5.29	Butyric 10.61	65	Brownish Black	86	19.32 (19.20)	57.59 (57.63)	7.28 (7.20)
$(C_8H_{11})_2MoO\left[\begin{array}{c} OOC \\ \\ OOC \end{array}\right]$	3.92	Oxalic 4.15	60	Black	81	23.20 (23.18)	52.31 (52.20)	5.11 (5.20)
$(C_8H_{11})_2MoO\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2 \\ \\ COO \\ \\ COO \end{array}\right]$	4.37	Malonic 4.49	64	Blackish Brown	80	22.25 (22.43)	53.41 (53.80)	5.68 (5.61)
$(C_8H_{11})_2MoO\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2 - COO \\ \\ CH_2 - COO \end{array}\right]$	4.95	Succinic 5.12	68	Brown	79	21.78 (21.71)	54.46 (54.31)	5.98 (5.89)
$(C_8H_{11})_2MoO(O_2CC_6H_5)_2$	3.22	Benzoic 6.62	61	Brown	83	16.98 (16.89)	63.56 (63.39)	5.59 (5.63)

TABLE 3—DETAILS OF THE PREPARATION, PROPERTIES AND ANALYSIS OF CARBOXYLATES OF $(C_8H_{11})_2WOCl_2$

Compound	$(C_8H_{11})_2WOCl_2$ taken (m moles)	Corresponding carboxylic acid added (m moles)	Reaction time (h)	Colour	Yield (%)	Analytical data (%)		
						W	C	H
$(C_8H_{11})_2WO(O_2CH)_2$	4.32	Formic 8.77	52	Brown	88	36.34 (36.48)	43.52 (43.66)	4.80 (4.76)
$(C_8H_{11})_2WO(O_2CC_2H_5)_2$	4.93	Propionic 9.96	60	Black	85	33.17 (33.07)	47.72 (47.50)	5.00 (5.04)
$(C_8H_{11})_2WO(O_2CC_2H_7)_2$	5.04	Butyric 10.29	60	Brownish Black	85	31.02 (31.27)	49.45 (49.00)	6.10 (6.12)
$(C_8H_{11})_2WO\left[\begin{array}{c} OOC \\ \\ OOC \end{array}\right]$	5.71	Oxalic 5.86	65	Black	80	36.41 (36.63)	42.61 (43.06)	4.53 (4.38)
$(C_8H_{11})_2WO\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2 \\ \\ COO \\ \\ COO \end{array}\right]$	5.94	Malonic 6.01	68	Blackish	80	35.93 (35.64)	44.61 (44.20)	4.53 (4.65)
$(C_8H_{11})_2WO\left[\begin{array}{c} CH_2 - COO \\ \\ CH_2 - COO \end{array}\right]$	5.85	Succinic 9.93	70	Brownish Black	78	34.84 (34.69)	44.96 (45.31)	4.93 (4.90)
$(C_8H_{11})_2WO(O_2CC_6H_5)_2$	5.01	Benzoic 5.21	65	Brown	81	28.42 (28.03)	54.66 (54.90)	4.76 (4.88)

Calcd. C, 54.06; H, 6.31; Mo, 21.61%). Other carboxylic derivatives of (A) were prepared similarly and the data regarding their preparation, properties and analysis are given in Table 2.

Preparation of Dicyclo-octadienyl Diacetato Tungsten Oxide :

To 2.25 g (4.64 m moles) of dicyclo-octadienyl tungsten oxy-dichloride taken in a 250 ml round bottom flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube, were added 150 ml of the solvent (dry benzene) and 0.56 g (9.33 m moles) of freshly distilled acetic acid. Hydrogen chloride gas did not evolve soon after the addition of acetic acid to dicyclo-octadienyl tungsten oxy-dichloride. The contents were then refluxed at 80°. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas started after about 15 minutes of the refluxing and the refluxing was continued till

the evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased (59 h). The contents were cooled to room temperature and the blackish brown solution obtained was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure (15-20 mm). The blackish brown product so obtained was repeatedly washed with dry benzene and upon subsequent drying under reduced pressure (1-2 mm) gave a deep brown crystalline compound (88% yield), the analysis of which corresponded with the formula $(C_8H_{11})_2WO(CH_3COO)_2$ (Found: C, 45.02; H, 5.29; W, 34.67 Calcd. C, 45.22; H, 5.27; W, 34.57%). Other carboxylic derivatives of (B) were prepared similarly and the data regarding their preparation, properties and analysis are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

Cyclo-octadienes are known to form addition complex. Recently we have reported(3) the reactions

of 1, 3-cyclo-octadiene with molybdenum oxy-tetrachloride and tungsten oxy-tetrachloride resulting in the formation of novel compounds with the general formula $(C_8H_{11})_2 MOCl_2$ ($M=Mo$ or W). These compounds represent the only examples in the literature where cyclo-octadiene is present as cyclo-octadienyl anion, $C_8H_{11}^-$.

Carboxylate Derivatives :

The compositions of the carboxylates of (A) and (B) indicate that in the case of mono-carboxylic acids one mole of (A) or (B) reacts with two moles of the acid, whereas in the case of dicarboxylic acids, only one mole of the acid reacts with one mole of (A) or (B). The formation of the carboxylates of (A) and (B) can be represented by the following general equation :

where :

- $M=Mo$ or W ,
 $A=$ Corresponding acid,
 $X=1, n=2$, for mono-carboxylic acids,
 $X'=2, n=1$, for di-carboxylic acids.

Carboxylates of (A) and (B) are coloured and crystalline compounds. They are thermally stable. They do not melt but decompose above 300° . They are insoluble in common organic solvents such as acetone, ethanol, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride but are slightly soluble in benzene.

Infrared Spectra :

Details of the infrared spectra of representative compounds are given in Table 1. The $C=O$ stretching vibrations (4-6) in all the carboxylates of (A) and (B) except the benzoic acid derivatives appear at 1715 cm^{-1} ; this vibration in benzoic acid derivatives appears at $\sim 1690\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The bands at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in case of propionic and butyric acid derivatives

of (A) and (B) are due to the presence of $-C-CH_2$ stretching vibrations(7) and these bands are absent in all other carboxylates. The bands at 3000 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the $C-H$ stretching frequency. $C=C$ stretching and $C-C$ stretching frequencies are associated with bands at $\sim 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at 900 cm^{-1} respectively. The $C-O-M$ band in all the compounds gives rise to a band at $\sim 1310\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The extra bands in the case of propionic and butyric acid derivatives of (A) and (B) at 1410 cm^{-1} are due to the presence of CH_2 group adjacent to $C=O$ group (8-10). The bands at $\sim 980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $\sim 750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are associated with Metal=Oxygen (11, 12) and Metal- C_8H_{11} (3) linkages respectively.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank Dr. S. K. Anand, Lecturer in Chemistry, Dayal Singh College, New Delhi for helpful discussions.

References

1. J. CHATT and L. M. VENANZI, *Nature*, 1956, 177, 852.
2. J. CHATT and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*; 1957, 4735.
3. K. K. MUNJAL, M. R. VERMA, K. M. SHARMA and R. P. SINGH, *J. Prakt. Chemie (Germany)*, 1974, 316, 928.
4. M. S. C. FLETT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 962.
5. P. J. GORISH and W. H. T. DAVISON, *J. Chem. Soc.*; 1955, 2428.
6. E. J. HARTWALL, R. E. RICHARDS and H. W. THOMPSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*; 1948, 1437.
7. N. K. FREEMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1859.
8. R. G. SINCLAIR, A. F. MCKAY and R. N. JONES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2570.
9. R. G. SINCLAIR, A. F. MCKAY, G. S. MYERS and R. N. JONES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2578.
10. S. A. FRANCIS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, 19, 942.
11. C. G. BARRACLOUGH, J. LEWIS and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.
12. K. M. SHARMA, S. K. ANAND, R. K. MULTANI and B. D. JAIN, *J. Organometallic. Chem.*, 1971, 28, 399.